

Higher Education and India: The need of Domain Centric Information Sciences for solid and Sustainable Development

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Abstract:

Indian Higher Education system is changing rapidly from the traditional systems. Indian Higher Education system is one of the largest in the world and it holds different kind of organizations and institutions which include the universities, colleges, polytechnics, research centers, Institute of National Importance (INI) etc. India holds more than forty thousand HEIs (Higher Educational Institutions) and diversity of nature of the program is also increasing. Computing field is important everywhere and every nation. The trends on Computing related education is also changing; initially only Computer Science was the field but gradually other branches of Computing have emerged. In Information track, many other branches have been developed viz. Information Technology, Informatics, Information Science, Information Management, Information Systems etc. These subjects are interdisciplinary in nature and getting more day by day. There are many universities have started academic programs in domain centric Information Sciences viz. Health Information Science, Business Information Sciences, Bio Information Sciences, Chemo Information Science, Library Information Sciences, Quantum Information Sciences and so on. These fields have been started in International universities and as a result specific field sectors are emerged and developed. India is a developing nation and growing rapidly and Education programs in this field is increasing as well. Though India holds different challenges in higher education but there are many ways in which such domain centric Information Science may be started. This paper has sought out many potentialities to launch the field in Indian education systems in detailed.

Keywords : Higher Education, Information Technology, Interdisciplinary Science, Higher Education, India, Developing Country

1. Introduction :

Information Science is changing rapidly due to its affiliation with other areas and technologies. The field is become more interdisciplinary day by day. The traditional components of Information Technology viz. Database Technology, Web Technology, Network Technology, Multimedia Technology, Software Technology are the base for the better Information Science practice. It is worthy to mention that, the latest emerging areas are also important and growing rapidly for the development of Information Science practice viz.—

- *Cloud Computing,*
- *Converged Computing and Networks,*
- *Network and Information Security*
- *Information Assurance*
- *Big Data and Data Analytics*
- *Data Science and Management*
- *Human Computer Interaction and UXD*
- *Usability Engineering*
- *Animation and VFX etc*
- *3D Printing and Information Architecture etc.*

It is worthy to note that, the domain based Information Sciences are the result of interaction and application of IT and Computing in other areas viz. Health Information Science, Geo Information Science, Bio Information Science, Chemo Information Science, Library Information Science, Business Information Science etc [1], [5].

The Indian higher education system is constituted with different types of educational institutes viz. Colleges, Universities, Institute of National Importance etc. The following sections have discussed these in detail.

2. Methods and Sources

The paper is conceptual in nature and deals with several Interdisciplinary affairs. *Due to the nature of* Techno-Educational affairs, the paper has been used different study method. *Moreover the work is also* having the Managerial Issues. The paper constituted both primary and secondary data. Review work play a leading role in this paper and thus review of literature has been undertaken. For this work, the study is conducted primarily as a case of private university regarding finding the latest availability of domain centric Information Science. Different private university websites are utilized to gather the current information on domain centric Information Science [2], [3].

3. Indian Higher Education

India is the leading educational system in the world having the rank first in the world. India holds about 800 universities. Here Table: 1 classified different types of universities in this regard—

- Government Universities (these are two types *State University i.e. Individual Provice/ State Funded & Management Universities and Central University (i.e. Funded & Managed by the Central Government)*)

- Self Financed Universities (*these are mainly Private Universities billed by the state legislative assembly*).
- Deemed Universities (*these are up-graded institutes to the Deemed University due to their excellence in education and research*).

India holds over 40000+ higher educational institutes in the areas of professional, general fields. Here important to note that few colleges also offers Master's Degree in many cases. Even some of the colleges approved as a Research Centre to offer Ph.D. and Doctoral Programs in some of the subjects [4], [7].

As per UGC website, total 94 Institutes of National Importance (INI) are exist and treated as good and reputed in Indian education system. Institutes of National Importance (INI) offers education and research programs leading to Engineering, Management, Basic & Applied Science, Architecture, Pharmaceutical Sciences, Medical Sciences streams. These are established and funded by the Central Government but treated as more valuable and important than central Universities. It is important to note that few institutions (*most of these are Research based*) are also established and funded by Govt. of India viz. Bose Institute, Saha Institute of Nuclear Physics etc. The type of institutes is about 200+.

Table: 1- Showing Indian Universities at a glance

Universities	In Numbers	Location
Central Universities	49	Pan India with 28 States and UT
State Universities	399	Pan India with 28 States and UT
State Private Universities	334	Except some states and UT
Deemed Universities	124	Except some states and UT
Institute of National Importance	94	Pan India basis

4. Information Science: Basics

Information Science is responsible for information affairs viz. collection, selection, organization, processing, management and dissemination. It deals with information and similar contents [8], [10]. Information Studies is very close with the Information Science but it deals with Computational tools and technologies. Information Science powered by IT components viz. *Networking Technologies, Multimedia Technologies, Database Technologies, Web Technologies*. It is worthy to note that in this field Management Sciences and Social Issues are core and most valuable in different context. Interaction of information-technology with people are the base for the development of this subject. The field Information Science is available in different nomenclatures viz.—

- Informatics
- Information Science and Technology (IST)
- Information Science and Computing (ISC)

- Information Science and Systems (ISS)
- Computer and Information Science (CIS)
- Information and Computer Science (ICS) etc

However it is important to note that the field Information Systems is also closely associated with the field in few contexts.

5. Information Science & Domain Based Context: Worldwide and Indian Picture

Hence it is a fact that, Information Science is community, society and people centric with strong relationship with other subjects thus several new areas, branches have been created by the integration of Information Science [9],[11]. It is worthy to note that, this field is popular and known as Informatics in European Countries whereas in USA as Information Science. In generally the Information Science branch may be classified into Pure Science based/ Bio Science based or Social Science based (*the details are depicted in Fig:1*). The details are mentioned as follows—

Fig: 1-The domain based Information Sciences at a glance

The details of the domain based Information Science is depicted and described as follows with its basic meaning and features.

Health Information Science/ Informatics

Health Science with Information Science developed Health Information Science. More clearly it is the application of Information Science and Technology into Healthcare affairs, Medical Systems, Hospital Management etc.

Chemo Information Science/ Informatics

The application of Information Science and Technology into Chemistry and Chemical Sciences lead the development of Chemo Informatics. In generally, the combination of Chemical Science and Information Science created the field. However this field has strong focus and application areas in Pharmacy and Allied Sciences.

Bio Information Science/ Informatics

Bio Information Science is a merged field of Bio Science and Information Science. The application of Computing and IT in Bio and allied areas is called as Bio Informatics in-generally. The field is applicable in different areas of Biology, Genetics, Health Science, Pharmacy and so on.

Geo Information Science/ Informatics

Geo Sciences and its integration with the Information Science results the field, Geo Information Science. More clearly, the application of Information Science and Technology into Geo and Allied areas results the field Geo Information Science. The core of the field is called Remote Sensing, Geo Information Systems, Geography and Environment, Disaster Management etc.

6. Domain Based Information Science and New Programs

It is important to note that these domain centric Information Science is offered and available as a program of study in various universities with different level of programs viz.

- Bachelors (leading to BSc/BS/other professional nomenclatures)
- Masters (leading to MSc/MS/other professional nomenclatures)
- Doctoral programs (leading to PhD and other professional nomenclatures)

It is noted that such programs are available in some cases in a single Department/ School/ Academic units. Many western countries offers the program as full degree viz. MS- Health Information Science and MS-Bio Informatics etc whereas in some Universities the program are offered as different specialization viz. MS- Information Science (Health Informatics/ Health Information Science) and MS- Information Science (Bio Informatics).

As far as India is concerned the programs are offered in limited number of institutes but having less interaction, communication and collaborative dealings. Importantly, Information Science programs in India not offered in a single umbrella.

7. Need of these Programs in Sustainable Development

The Information Science programs has been started in different universities in abroad and in recent past various other universities have started the programs [6], [12]. This study notice the development following three areas in private universities as most available domain specific Information Sciences program viz.

- Bio Informatics
- Geo Informatics
- Health Informatics (including Nursing Informatics)
- Chem Informatics

The traditional Information Science area called Library and Information Science simply treated as LIS not considered in this study *as from long back Library Science program/subject was there as a study and program. And new nomenclature adopted in different universities. All these subjects are required for the solid and sustainable development in different sectors viz.—*

- Biological Sector/ Industry
- Geographical/ Environmental Sector/ Industry
- Healthcare/ Medical Sector/ Industry
- Chemical/ Pharmaceutical area/ Sector etc

The table: 2 depicted the domain centric Information Sciences in Indian Private University at a glance except LIS.

Table: 2-Domain centric Information Sciences in Indian Private University

Domain centric Information Sciences in Indian Private University		
	Universities	
1	Himalayan University	BSc-Bio Informatics MSc-Bio Informatics MSc-Geo Informatics
2	Amity University, Haryana	BTech-Bio Informatics
3	Jaipur National University	BSc-Bio Informatics MSc-Bio Informatics
4	Mahatma Jyoti Rao Phoole University	BTech-Bio Informatics
5	Mody University of Science and Technology	PGD in Bio Informatics
6	Shridhar University	MSc-Bio Informatics
7	Singhania University	BSc-Bio Informatics MTech- Bio Informatics MTech-Chem Informatics
8	Amity University, Noida	BTech-Bio Informatics BSc-Geo Informatics MSc-Geo Informatics MTech-Geo Informatics
9	Galgotias University	MSc-Bio Informatics
10	IFTM University	MSc-Bio Informatics MTech-Bio Informatics
11	Maharishi University of Information Technology	MSc-Bio Informatics
12	The Neotia University	MSc-Bio Technology & Bio Informatics

13	Pragyan International University	MSc-Geo Informatics
14	NIIT University	MTech-GIS
15	Sangam University	MSc-Geo Informatics
16	Shri Jagdish Prasad Jhabarmal Tibrewala University	MSc-GIS
17	Sikkim Manipal University	PGD in Geo Informatics
18	Shiv Nadar University, Gautam Budh Nagar, UP	PhD- Chem Informatics
19	Institute of Trans-Disciplinary Health Sciences and Technology University,	MSc-CS (Health Informatics) Integrated MSc-CS (Health Informatics)
20	Chitkara University, Punjab	MBA (Health IT) with Fortis
21	Mahatma Gandhi University of Medical Sciences & Technology	BSc-Health Informatics MSc-Health Informatics PG Certificate in Nursing Informatics PG Certificate in Health Informatics PG Diploma in Nursing Informatics PG Diploma in Health Informatics
22	University of Petroleum and Energy Studies, UK	BTech-CSE (Healthcare Informatics (all with IBM))

8. Conclusion

The world is changing rapidly information and knowledge systems changing rapidly due to advancement of information technologies. And for the development in diverse field, Information Science play a leading role. The IS field is constituted with information fundamentals and information management. For the promotion of interdisciplinary research Information Sciences play a vital and leading role. Various fields such as Information Systems, Informatics, Data Science, Information Management etc are already a great name in information promotion and development and here individual field specific development become possible by the initiation of new age and interdisciplinary Information Science programs viz. Health Informatics, Bio Informatics, Geo Informatics etc. Many private universities in India have started program in general Information Science (*without domain focus*) and also domain centric Information Science though more tie-up, collaboration, sharing etc. Hence by this solid and healthy development of these areas and sectors are positively possible.

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